

Oxalatotitanates

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The preparation of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases *viz.*, $(\text{BH})_2\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ and $(\text{B}'\text{H}_2)\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$, where B = pyridine, quinoline and guanidine and B' = ethylenediamine and propylenediamine are described. The TGA and DTA data of the compounds indicate the formation of TiOCO_2 as an unstable intermediate around 300° . The I.R. data show the compounds to be chelate oxalato complexes.

THE oxalatotitanates¹⁻⁷ are of two types, *viz.*, $\text{M}^1[\text{Ti}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3]$, where $\text{M}^1 = (\text{CH}_3)_4\text{N}$, and $\text{M}_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$ where $\text{M} = \text{Na}, \text{K}, (\text{pyridine H})^+, \frac{1}{3} \text{Ba}$, etc. The above compounds were studied extensively by others^{1-7, 17, 18}. In the present work the isolation of oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases, $(\text{BH})_2\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$ and $(\text{B}'\text{H}_2)\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2$, (where B = pyridine, quinoline and guanidine; B' = ethylenediamine and propylenediamine), are described. The preparation of pyridinium compound reported in this paper was prepared by a method different from that reported by Van de Valde *et al*⁷.

From the reaction of potassium oxalatotitanate with hexamminecobalt(III) chloride Marcarovici *et al*⁵ isolated the compound $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{Ti}_3\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_6] \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (I). They further reported that this compound on heating at 170° produces $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_3$ (II). But in the present work, the compound (II) was obtained directly from the reaction of potassium oxalatotitanate with $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]\text{Cl}_3$ in aqueous medium, and it was found to correspond to the formula $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$. All the compounds are studied through recording of their I.R. spectra, TGA and DTA data.

Experimental

Hexamminecobalt(III) nitrate, hexamminecobalt(III) chloride and potassium oxalatotitanate

were prepared by standard methods⁹⁻¹¹. Titanium, cobalt and oxalate were estimated by usual standard methods and nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Dumas' method. The analytical data of the compounds are given in Table 1. Hydrated titanium oxide used in the present work was prepared according to Rosenheim and Schutte².

Pyridinium oxalatotitanate, $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{NH}]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Hydrated titanium oxide obtained from titanium dioxide was dissolved in a solution of oxalic acid by heating on a water bath. To this solution pyridine was added and the mixture was evaporated on a water bath, cooled and absolute alcohol was added when the compound precipitated out. Filtered, washed with water and with alcohol. The compound was recrystallised from water in the presence of 2-3 drops of pyridine. It was dried to constant weight in air.

The corresponding oxalatotitanates of protonated quinoline, guanidine, propylenediamine and ethylenediamine are obtained in the above manner from calculated amounts of reactants but without the addition of alcohol required for crystallisation. The amines were, however, reacted with calculated amounts of oxalic acid before adding the mixture to hydrated titania dissolved in oxalic acid. The recrystallisation step was also found to be unnecessary.

Hexamminecobalt(III) oxalatotitanate $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$: The compound

TABLE—1

Compounds	Found (%)			Calculated (%)		
	N	Ti	Oxalate	N	Ti	Oxalate
$[\text{PyH}]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	6.25	10.71	39.13	6.17	10.55	38.77
$[\text{QH}]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	5.33	9.31	33.39	5.31	9.09	33.40
$[\text{GuH}]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	21.78	12.95	45.54	21.71	12.98	45.47
$[\text{EnH}_2]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	8.72	14.99	54.05	8.75	14.97	55.01
$[\text{PnH}_2]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2] \cdot 0.4\text{H}_2\text{O}$	8.43	14.85	54.39	8.66	14.82	54.45
$[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_6]_2[\text{TiO}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]_3 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$	14.10	12.00	43.17	14.38	12.31	45.23

Py = pyridine, Q = quinoline, En = ethylenediamine, Pn = propylenediamine, Gu = guanidine.

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was obtained as a yellow precipitate on adding a solution (40 ml) of hexamminecobalt(III) chloride (1.7 gm) to a solution (75 ml) of potassium oxalatotitanate, $K_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 2H_2O$ (3.5 gm). The precipitate was filtered, washed with water and alcohol, and dried in air. The same product was also obtained on adding a solution of hexamminecobalt(III) nitrate to a solution of hydrated titanium oxide in oxalic acid.

The oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases are soluble in water but the corresponding hexamminecobalt(III) compound is insoluble in water. All of them are insoluble in common organic solvents. These compounds when dehydrated over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator at room temperature lose water giving anhydrous compounds. The TGA and DTA data were recorded in manually operated instruments by heating the compounds at the rate of $5^\circ/\text{min}$. The I.R. data were recorded in a Perkin-Elmer apparatus in KBr in the range $400-4000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.

Results and Discussion

The oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases are found to be thermally stable up to 50° . The thermograms of the oxalatotitanates of protonated quinoline, guanidine and ethylenediamine show horizontal stretches in the temperature ranges, $80-110^\circ$, $100-200^\circ$ and $140-170^\circ$ respectively corresponding to the loss of water of crystallisation. The pyrolysis curves did not show the formation of any stable intermediate compound.

From the TGA and DTA data (Figs. 1 and 2) it may be concluded that probably $TiOCO_2$ is formed

Fig. 1. T.G.A. and D.T.A. of oxalatotitanates.

$[EnH_3][TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot H_2O$: $\circ-\circ-$; ———
 $[PyH_3][TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 3H_2O$: $\bullet-\bullet-$; - - - - -
 $[QH_3][TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 1.5H_2O$: $\bullet-\bullet-$; - . - . - .

as an unstable intermediate (indicated by the endotherms in the DTA curves) in the range $280-330^\circ$ from the oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases except in the case of the corresponding quinolinium compound. $TiOCO_2$ then undergoes decomposition to titanium dioxide with the evolution of CO_2 (indicated by exothermic reaction). Another interesting feature noted in the thermal study of the

Fig. 2. T.G.A. and D.T.A. data of oxalatotitanates and hydrated titanium dioxide.

$[PnH_3][TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 0.H_2O$: $\circ-\circ-$; ———
 $[GUH_3][TiO(C_2O_4)_2] \cdot 1.5.H_2O$: $\bullet-\bullet-$;
 $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2]_3$: $\square-\square-$; - - - - -
 $TiO_2 \cdot 1.5H_2O$: $\bullet-\bullet-$; - . - . - .

oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases is that the differential thermograms show broad and ill-defined exotherms probably due to the transformation of amorphous titanium dioxide into crystalline form⁷. The above fact is supported by the DTA of hydrated titanium oxide and titanil oxalate which show sharp exotherms in the range $400-420^\circ$ ¹¹ (Fig. 2). The TGA and DTA data of $[Co(NH_3)_6]_2[TiO(C_2O_4)_2]_3$ do not show any remarkable feature. The compound was found to be stable up to 50° . The residue obtained after thermal analysis was found to be the oxides of cobalt and titanium. The exotherm at 370° probably corresponds to the formation of the oxides of cobalt and titanium⁸.

The bands for oxalate group in the regions $1720-1750\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1380-1430\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $785-825\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $520-570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to the chelate oxalate complexes¹³⁻¹⁵. The bands for oxalate group observed in the I.R. spectra of the oxalatotitanates of protonated organic bases and of hexamminecobalt(III) ion lie within the regions given above. This suggests that these oxalato complexes are chelate complexes.

The lattice water usually absorb in the regions, $3200-3550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (antisymmetric and symmetric OH stretching) and at $1600-1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (HOH bending)¹⁶. Similarly, bands of N-H also occur in the regions $3000-3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1550-1650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1400-1470\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The oxalatotitanates described here show bands in the regions $2900-3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1650-1740\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1500-1530\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1300-1480\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to H_2O , N-H and C_2O_4 group as indicated above. The band due to HOH bending at $1600-1630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ could not be identified separately due to the superimposition of the band with the O-C-O asymmetric stretching. All the compounds show broad bands in the region $800-900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may be due to Ti-O stretchings¹²⁻¹³;

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